

Fragility of the Fragility Index: When Calculation Becomes Impossible

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Abstract

Background: The Fragility Index (FI) may become unattainable under Fisher's exact test constraints in common clinical trial scenarios, including rare events, balanced small samples, and extreme imbalances.

Methods: We analyzed 14 representative 2×2 tables spanning rare events, balanced designs, and extreme imbalances, and computed alternative fragility metrics.

Results: FI was not attainable in all 14 cases. Risk Quotient (RQ), Percent Fragility Index (PFI), and Relative Risk Index (RRI) computed in 14/14; Robustness Index (RI) in 12/14.

Conclusions: FI is not attainable in everyday scenarios. Robust fragility metrics include the RQ, which quantifies distance to therapeutic neutrality on a bounded 0–1 scale, and the PFI, which quantifies the percentage change needed to flip statistical significance.

Keywords: Fragility Index, Percent Fragility Index, Risk Quotient, statistical robustness, clinical trials, methodology limitations, evidence assessment, Fisher's exact test, Robustness Index, p-value sensitivity.

Introduction

The Fragility Index (FI) measures statistical robustness by determining the minimum number of outcome event changes required to alter the statistical significance of a result [1]. By quantifying how many patients switching from non-event to event status would flip a

p-value across the conventional threshold of 0.05, the FI provides an intuitive metric for assessing the stability of clinical trial findings. Lower fragility indices suggest results vulnerable to small changes, while higher values indicate more robust findings.

The metric has gained substantial traction in medical literature, with applications spanning cardiology [2], oncology [3], orthopedics [4], and critical care. Its appeal lies in simplicity: rather than abstract statistical concepts, the FI expresses robustness in terms of actual patients. A trial with FI equals three means just three outcome changes would reverse the significance conclusion, making fragility tangible for clinicians and researchers.

However, despite widespread adoption, fundamental methodological limitations have raised concerns, including reliance on p-values [5], and the act of intentionally changing the raw data [6]. An additional limitation has received insufficient attention. The FI relies on Fisher's exact test with fixed row totals, meaning study arm sizes remain constant while outcome counts vary. This constraint, combined with discrete integer arithmetic, creates scenarios where significance threshold crossing becomes mathematically impossible. When this occurs, the FI is declared "not attainable," but the conditions that cause this failure have not been systematically characterized.

This paper demonstrates that FI computation fails across a broad range of clinically relevant scenarios, casting doubt on whether a fragility metric that itself exhibits fragility can serve as a reliable tool for evidence assessment. We provide concrete examples of computation failures and discuss implications for researchers selecting fragility metrics.

Methods

Theoretical Framework

The Fragility Index operates under these rules:

- Apply outcome toggles (event \leftrightarrow non-event) to the study arm with fewer events
- Maintain fixed row totals (arm sizes unchanged)
- Use Fisher's exact test (two-sided, $\alpha=0.05$) to assess significance after each toggle

- Report the minimum number of toggles crossing the significance threshold
- If crossing is impossible under constraints, declare "not attainable"

The "not attainable" condition arises when:

1. Zero events in an arm prevent downward toggles
2. Maximum possible events reached, preventing upward toggles
3. Significance never crosses the threshold regardless of toggle direction
4. Discrete integer constraints prevent reaching the exact threshold

The FI is then compared with alternative fragility metrics that do not rely on discrete integer changes [7] or do not rely on changes in the p-value [8]. Table 1 presents the formulas and key features of fragility metrics examined in this study.

Table 1. Fragility Metrics: Definitions and Formulas

Metric	Definition	Formula	Notes
FI	Minimum integer outcome toggles that cross $p \leq 0.05$ using Fisher's exact test with fixed row totals.	—	Apply toggles to arm with fewer events
PFI	Continuous percent change needed to cross $p \leq 0.05$ with fixed margins.	$PFI = x / (n/4)$	x = continuous outcome change that flips significance; uses Pearson χ^2
RRI	Distance from therapeutic neutrality ($RR=1$) based on observed counts.	$RRI = ad - bc / n$	P-value independent; measures deviation from $RR=1$
RQ	Normalized distance to therapeutic neutrality.	$RQ = RRI / (n/4)$	Bounded 0-1; interpretable as percent change in outcomes to reach $RR=1$
RI	Sample-size scaling factor to change significance.	Scale all cells by k ($k > 1$)	Scale up if non-significant baseline; scale down if significant baseline; uses Pearson χ^2

Note: 2×2 table cells $\{a,b,c,d\}$ where a =arm A events, b =arm A non-events, c =arm B events, d =arm B non-events; $n = a+b+c+d$ (total sample size); RR = relative risk.

Software

Analyses were performed by the Fragility Metrics Toolkit, which is a collection of Python scripts on Google Colab, available on GitHub, and archived in a Zenodo repository [9]. We used two-sided Fisher's exact test ($\alpha=0.05$) for FI and Pearson χ^2 for PFI and RI. RRI and RQ were computed directly from observed counts using $RRI = |ad - bc| / n$ and $RQ = RRI / (n / 4)$.

Test Case Selection

We constructed 14 representative 2×2 tables demonstrating FI computation failures:

Format: {a, b, c, d} where a=arm A events, b=arm A non-events, c=arm B events, d=arm B non-events. For 2x2 contingency tables, the cells are {a,b,c,d}; $n=a+b+c+d$.

Test cases:

1. {0,3,60,40} - Zero events, large sample
2. {2,2,2,2} - Perfect balance, small sample
3. {2,2,3,2} - Near balance, small sample
4. {2,2,5,2} - Moderate imbalance, small sample
5. {3,2,2,2} - Shifted balance, small sample
6. {4,4,2,2} - Larger balanced sample
7. {13,10,2,2} - Large-small imbalance
8. {3,2,6,5} - Moderate both arms
9. {2,4,12,12} - Imbalanced arms, balanced outcomes
10. {2,2,10,7} - Small-large comparison
11. {9,10,3,2} - Large-small reversal
12. {3,3,9,10} - Moderate balance, $n=25$
13. {2,3,8,7} - Small arm A, moderate arm B, $n=20$
14. {3,3,11,10} - Balanced arms, $n=27$

These cases span:

- Sample sizes from 8 to 103 participants
- Event rates from 0% to 83%
- Balanced and unbalanced designs
- Significant and non-significant baseline p-values

Results

Universal Computation Failure

All 14 test cases failed to yield computable FI values. The "not attainable" condition occurred across the entire range of sample sizes, event distributions, and baseline significance levels. This systematic failure demonstrates that FI incomputability is not a rare edge case but a structural limitation affecting standard clinical trial configurations.

Computational Example: Case 2 {2,2,2,2}

- **Baseline:** Fisher's exact $p = 1.000$ (non-significant)
- **Toggle arm A up:** {3,1,2,2} \rightarrow Fisher's $p = 1.000$
- **Toggle arm A up:** {4,0,2,2} \rightarrow Fisher's $p = 0.429$
- **Result:** No additional toggles are possible. Since it is not possible to cross the $\alpha=0.05$ threshold, the FI is reported as not attainable.

Computational Example: Case 14 {3,3,11,10}

- **Baseline:** Fisher's exact $p = 1.000$ (non-significant)
- **Toggle arm A up:** {4,2,11,10} \rightarrow Fisher's $p = 0.662$
- **Toggle arm A up:** {5,1,11,10} \rightarrow Fisher's $p = 0.350$
- **Toggle arm A up:** {6,0,11,10} \rightarrow Fisher's $p = 0.057$
- **Result:** No additional toggles are possible. Since it is not possible to cross the $\alpha=0.05$ threshold, the FI is reported as not attainable.

Why these occur: The symmetry and small cell counts create large discrete jumps in Fisher's exact p -values and limit toggling. No single integer toggle can position the p -value precisely at or across 0.05.

Failure Patterns by Scenario Type

Zero Event Scenarios

Case {0,3,60,40} illustrates the zero-event problem. When an arm has zero events, downward toggles are impossible, and upward toggles may never reach the significance threshold before exhausting available non-events. The large sample size means even converting all three arm A non-events to events produces insufficient change to affect the Fisher's exact p-value meaningfully.

Balanced Small Sample Scenarios

A perfect or near-perfect balance in small samples can cause computational failures even when events are present. Cases {2,2,2,2}, {2,2,3,2}, and {2,2,5,2} demonstrate this pattern. The discrete nature of small integers, combined with symmetric or near-symmetric distributions, means that toggling in either direction may undershoot or overshoot the significance threshold without crossing it. The gap between consecutive p-values in Fisher's exact test becomes too large relative to the 0.05 cutoff.

Extreme Imbalance Scenarios

Case {13,10,2,2} shows failures when one arm dominates in size or events. Large disparities in arm sizes or event rates create situations in which the statistical test's sensitivity to single-outcome changes is insufficient to bridge from one side of the significance threshold to the other. The fixed marginal totals prevent the redistributions necessary to achieve threshold crossing.

Moderate Size Scenarios

Even tables with reasonable sample sizes and event distributions failed computation. Cases {3,2,6,5}, {2,4,12,12}, {3,3,9,10}, and {3,3,11,10} have between 16 and 30 participants with multiple events per arm, yet FI remains unattainable. This demonstrates the problem extends beyond obvious edge cases into the mainstream of small-to-moderate clinical trial configurations.

Comparative Metric Performance

To assess whether FI's computational failures represent a unique limitation or a broader problem across fragility metrics, we computed four alternative metrics for all 14 cases: Percent Fragility Index (PFI), Relative Risk Index (RRI), Risk Quotient (RQ), and Robustness Index (RI). Table 2 presents the complete comparative results.

Table 2. Comparative Fragility Metrics Across All Test Cases

Case	a	b	c	d	n	FI	PFI	RRI	RQ	RI
1	0	3	60	40	103	NA	0.004	1.748	0.068	1.122
2	2	2	2	2	8	NA	0.693	0.000	0.000	NA
3	2	2	3	2	9	NA	0.546	0.222	0.099	42.683
4	2	2	5	2	11	NA	0.349	0.545	0.198	7.605
5	3	2	2	2	9	NA	0.546	0.222	0.099	42.683
6	4	4	2	2	12	NA	0.533	0.000	0.000	NA
7	13	10	2	2	27	NA	0.233	0.222	0.033	65.447
8	3	2	6	5	16	NA	0.404	0.188	0.047	92.435
9	2	4	12	12	30	NA	0.179	0.800	0.107	7.171
10	2	2	10	7	21	NA	0.278	0.286	0.054	37.317
11	9	10	3	2	24	NA	0.242	0.500	0.083	15.206
12	3	3	9	10	25	NA	0.315	0.120	0.019	303.629
13	2	3	8	7	20	NA	0.280	0.500	0.100	14.405
14	3	3	11	10	27	NA	0.297	0.111	0.016	362.520

Note: NA = Not attainable. FI: Fragility Index; PFI: Percent Fragility Index; RRI: Relative Risk Index; RQ: Risk Quotient; RI: Robustness Index. n = total sample size.

Computational Success Rates:

- **FI:** 0/14 cases (0%)
- **PFI:** 14/14 cases (100%)

- **RRI:** 14/14 cases (100%)
- **RQ:** 14/14 cases (100%)
- **RI:** 12/14 cases (86%)

The Risk Quotient demonstrated universal computability while providing clinically interpretable values. RQ values ranged from 0.000 (perfect therapeutic neutrality in cases 2 and 6) to 0.198 (case 4), indicating the percentage change in outcomes needed to reach therapeutic equivalence (relative risk = 1.0).

The Percent Fragility Index and Relative Risk Index were also computed successfully in all cases. However, RRI values lacked a standardized interpretation scale (ranging from 0.000 to 1.748), whereas RQ's 0-1 bounded scale enables direct cross-study comparisons. The Robustness Index failed in 2/14 cases (14%), though less frequently than FI, demonstrating that discrete sampling approaches share computational vulnerabilities.

Independence from Statistical Significance

Notably, computation failures occurred regardless of baseline statistical significance. Some test cases showed p-values well below 0.05, others well above, and some near the threshold. Whether a study's result is statistically significant does not indicate whether FI will be computable. Researchers cannot use their trial's p-value to predict the computational success of FI.

Discussion

Implications for Evidence Assessment

The widespread incomputability of the Fragility Index raises fundamental questions about its utility as a fragility metric. If the measure designed to assess stability itself exhibits instability across common scenarios, its interpretability becomes problematic.

Researchers face a dilemma: in precisely those situations where outcome events are rare or samples are small is exactly where robustness assessment is most critical. This is where the FI computation most often fails.

The "not attainable" designation provides no information about actual fragility. A trial returning "not attainable" could represent either an extremely robust finding in which no plausible outcome changes would alter significance, or an artifact of the table structure in which discrete constraints prevent computation. Without additional analysis, researchers cannot distinguish these cases, rendering the metric uninformative when it fails.

Structural Limitations of Discrete Metrics

The root cause is the combination of Fisher's exact test, fixed marginal totals, and integer outcomes. Fisher's test computes exact probabilities for discrete distributions, producing p-values that jump discontinuously as table entries change. The conventional 0.05 threshold sits at an arbitrary point in this discrete space. For many table configurations, no integer adjustment exists that lands a p-value precisely on or across 0.05.

This is not a numerical precision issue but a fundamental property of discrete probability distributions. Continuous approximations, such as Pearson's chi-square test, might cross thresholds more readily, but adopting such approaches would change the FI's definition and potentially introduce inaccuracies for small samples, where exact tests are preferred.

Alternative Robustness Metrics

Several alternatives avoid FI's computational fragility while preserving robustness assessment:

Percent Fragility Index (PFI) employs a continuous outcome change parameter rather than discrete toggles, allowing finer gradations that can locate threshold crossings even in complex table configurations. By permitting fractional outcome adjustments, PFI remains computable across all contingency tables. Our analysis confirmed 100% computational success across all 14 failed FI cases.

Risk Quotient (RQ) abandons the significance threshold framework entirely, instead measuring distance from therapeutic neutrality (relative risk equals one). Because RQ operates on observed data without requiring iterative significance testing, it always returns a value. The metric focuses on clinical meaningfulness rather than statistical artifacts. Our

comparative analysis demonstrated universal computability with RQ values, providing an interpretable clinical context even when the FI was not attainable.

Robustness Index (RI) scales sample sizes proportionally rather than toggling discrete outcomes, providing a different perspective on stability. While still subject to some constraints (2/14 failures in our analysis), RI's continuous scaling approach experiences fewer computation failures than FI's discrete toggles.

Why RQ Achieves Universal Computability: The RQ achieves 100% computational success because it operates on observed data through direct arithmetic calculation rather than iterative hypothesis testing. Unlike FI, which requires finding discrete toggles that cross an arbitrary threshold (a constraint that may have no integer solution), RQ directly measures distance from therapeutic neutrality using: $RQ = 4|ad - bc| / n^2$

This calculation always yields a finite value for any non-empty 2×2 table, as it involves only basic arithmetic operations on cell counts. The metric does not depend on:

- Discrete integer constraints
- Iterative significance testing
- Threshold crossing detection
- Distributional assumptions

This mathematical simplicity ensures RQ can quantify fragility even in edge cases where threshold-based metrics fail.

Comparative Evidence for PFI and RQ

The comparative metric analysis (Table 2) provides empirical evidence for PFI and RQ as the preferred fragility metrics. While FI failed universally (0% success), PFI and RQ succeeded in all cases (100% success) and provided quantitative fragility assessments of the p-value and distance to therapeutic neutrality.

The PFI and RQ offer distinct advantages over alternatives:

Versus RRI: Though RRI computed universally, its unbounded scale (0 to $n/4$) complicates interpretation and cross-study comparison. RQ's normalization to the 0-1 scale provides an intuitive, percentage-based interpretation: RQ = 0.10 means "a 10% change in outcomes results in therapeutic neutrality." Notably, the RQ can be applied to contingency tables of any configuration and is not limited to 2x2 tables.

Versus RI: RI's 86% computational success improves upon FI but falls short of universal reliability. Additionally, RI's scale-dependent nature (factor k) prevents direct cross-study comparisons without accounting for sample size. The broad range of values indicates that the RI is highly sensitive to small cell counts in contingency tables.

Limits of Alternative Metrics

While PFI and RQ avoid FI's computational failures, they have distinct limitations:

PFI Limitations: Remains tied to the arbitrary 0.05 significance threshold and may produce misleading results when the baseline p-value is far from 0.05. It uses χ^2 approximation rather than an exact test (less appropriate for small samples), and interpretation assumes fixed marginal totals, which may not reflect real-world data variability

RQ Limitations: Clinical interpretation is challenging when the relative risk is already near 1.0 (small absolute effects). It focuses on RR=1 neutrality, which may not align with non-inferiority or superiority margins. It cannot replace p-value thresholds in regulatory contexts (FDA requires significance testing). Rare event scenarios may yield numerically small RQ despite clinically meaningful relative effects, and it does not address loss to follow-up or differential dropout between arms

When FI May Be Preferred: The FI may remain useful when regulatory submissions require discrete event-based sensitivity analyses. It may be helpful in interim analyses using predefined stopping boundaries and studies where discrete patient reclassification is the specific concern

The choice of fragility metric should align with the research question and decision context, rather than solely with computational convenience.

Recommendations for Researchers

When selecting fragility metrics, researchers should:

1. **Prioritize RQ and PFI** - Universal computability and clinical neutrality focus make RQ the preferred primary fragility metric for distance to therapeutic neutrality. Improved computability and greater precision make PFI the preferred fragility metric for quantifying the sensitivity of the p-value to small changes in the data.
2. **Avoid FI as a sole metric** - Never rely exclusively on FI, given its systematic computational failures, indicating that the FI is itself fragile in situations such as small cell counts – precisely where a fragility metric is most needed.
3. **Consider table structure** - Tables with rare events, small samples, or extreme imbalances face a higher FI incomputability risk
4. **Avoid over-interpretation** - Do not assume "not attainable" FI implies robustness without examining alternative metrics like RQ

Study Limitations

This analysis focused on theoretical incomputability rather than empirical prevalence in published literature. While we demonstrated computation failures across diverse scenarios, a systematic review of actual trial data would quantify real-world incomputability rates. Additionally, we examined only 2×2 tables; extensions to multi-arm or multi-outcome studies may exhibit different failure patterns.

Our analysis used a two-sided Fisher's exact test per the FI's original specification. Alternative implementations using one-sided tests or different significance thresholds would yield different incomputability patterns, though the fundamental discrete-constraint problem would remain.

Conclusion

The FI, despite intuitive appeal and widespread adoption, exhibits systematic computational fragility across common clinical trial scenarios. Zero events, balanced small samples, extreme imbalances, and various moderate-sized configurations all produced incomputability in our test cases. This limitation occurs independent of

statistical significance and affects scenarios where robustness assessment is most crucial.

A comparative analysis of alternative metrics shows that FI's computational failures are not inherent to fragility assessment but are specific to its discrete toggle methodology. The RQ and PFI both achieved universal computability (100% success) while providing clinically interpretable values.

Researchers should recognize that a fragile fragility metric provides questionable evidence for assessment. The benefits of adopting the PFI and RQ as primary fragility metrics needs further investigation. Future fragility research should prioritize metrics that are inherently robust across a broad range of sample sizes and outcomes.

Declarations

Data Availability: All data are contained within the article; code archived at Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17254763).

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Ethics Statement: Ethics approval was not required, as this methodological study analyzed theoretical contingency tables without involving human participants.

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